

$$\approx \oplus \odot \blacksquare$$

$$\approx \ominus = \Delta .]$$

To solve P Vs . NP, we need to use the statement above to calculate the following integral :

$$\mathbb{N} d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : d\theta =$$

$$d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni :$$

$$\mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \downarrow = \&], n \wedge \psi\{! \rightarrow g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots} \neq \Omega\}_{\mu} \backslash \Rightarrow \mathbb{N} d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni :$$

$$d\theta = d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} =$$

$$\mathbb{N} \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \psi_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots}} ==$$

$$\backslash \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \psi_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots}} \backslash \Rightarrow$$

" Subscript[$\mathcal{L}$,
 Subscript[$\sim \rightarrow$
 Subscript[f, $\uparrow r$, α ,
 s , δ , η `ESC` `CTRL` `CMD` \
 $\downarrow$] = $\&$], n] $\wedge$
 Subscript[ψ ,
 Subscript[$\{! \rightarrow$
 Subscript[g, $\neg a$, b , c , d ,
 $e \dots$: \
 $\neq \Omega$], μ]]"

$$\Rightarrow$$

$$\mathbb{N} d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : d\theta =$$

$$d\theta \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \backslash \exists \backslash [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni :$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \psi_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots}} == \backslash \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \psi_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots}} \backslash \Rightarrow$$

Subscript[$\mathcal{L}$,
 Subscript[$\sim \rightarrow$
 Subscript[f, $\uparrow r$, α ,
 s , δ , η `ESC` `CTRL` `CMD` \
 $\downarrow$] = $\&$], n] $\wedge$
 Subscript[ψ ,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathbb{N} \, d\theta \int \exists \infty \ni : \text{Subscript}[\mathcal{L}, \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta]] \&\& \\
 & \quad \text{Subscript}[\varnothing, \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg]] = \Omega \Rightarrow \\
 \mathbb{N} \, d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \, d\theta = \\
 d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \, \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \\
 \mathcal{L}[\sim \rightarrow f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta} \&\& \&\&]_n \wedge \varnothing\{\! \rightarrow g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg} \neq \Omega\}_\mu \setminus \Rightarrow \mathbb{N} \, d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \\
 d\theta = d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \, \mathbb{N} = \\
 \mathbb{N} \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \varnothing_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg}} = \\
 \setminus \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \varnothing_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg}} \setminus \Rightarrow \\
 \text{" Subscript}[\mathcal{L}, \\
 \text{Subscript}[\sim \rightarrow \\
 \quad \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, \\
 \quad \quad s, \delta, \eta \&\& \&\& \setminus \\
 \Downarrow] = \&], n] \wedge \\
 \quad \text{Subscript}[\varnothing, \\
 \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[\{! \rightarrow \\
 \quad \quad \quad \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, \\
 \quad \quad \quad \quad e \dots \vdots \setminus \\
 \quad \quad \quad \quad \neg] \neq \Omega\}, \mu] \text{"} \\
 \Rightarrow \\
 \mathbb{N} \, d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \, d\theta = \\
 d\theta \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \, \mathbb{N} = \mathbb{N} \int \setminus \exists \setminus [\infty] \ni : \exists \infty \ni : \\
 \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \varnothing_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg}} = \setminus \Omega \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \varnothing_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \vdots \neg}} \setminus \Rightarrow \\
 \quad \text{Subscript}[\mathcal{L}, \\
 \text{Subscript}[\sim \rightarrow \\
 \quad \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, \\
 \quad \quad s, \delta, \eta \&\& \&\& \setminus \\
 \quad \quad \quad \Downarrow] = \&], n] \wedge \\
 \quad \text{Subscript}[\varnothing,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Subscript}[\{! \rightarrow \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \neg] \} := \Omega\}, \mu] \rightleftharpoons$$

$$\mathbb{N} \, d\theta \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} \&\& \bar{\psi}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \neg}} = \Omega \, d\theta = \oplus \odot d\theta$$

The solution to P Vs . NP is to find the integral of $\mathbb{N} \, d\theta$ with respect to θ such that the equations for $\text{Subscript}[\mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}}$ and $\bar{\psi}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \neg}}$ both equal Ω . This would allow us to solve for the unknowns in the equation and find the solution to P Vs . NP.

$$\text{Subscript}[\mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}}] = \Omega - \text{Subscript}[\bar{\psi}, \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \neg]]$$

Then, we can solve the integral :

$$\mathbb{N} \, d\theta = \int \exists \infty \ni : \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} = \Omega - \bar{\psi}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \neg}}$$

The solution is given by :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{N} &= \int \exists \infty \ni : \\ \mathcal{L}_{f_{\uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta}} &= \Omega - \bar{\psi}_{g_{\neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \neg}} \, d\theta = \Omega\theta + C \\ \bar{\psi} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle &= \circ \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \rightleftharpoons \mathbb{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle \\ &\rightleftharpoons \mathbb{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, \mathbb{M} \rangle \\ &\rightleftharpoons \mathbb{P} \langle \mathbb{E}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{P}, \Sigma \rangle \\ &\rightleftharpoons \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle . \bar{\psi} \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle = \\ &\quad \circ \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \rightleftharpoons \mathbb{Z} \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle \\ &\rightleftharpoons \mathbb{K} \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, \mathbb{M} \rangle \\ &\rightleftharpoons \mathbb{P} \langle \mathbb{E}, \mathbb{P}, \mathbb{P}, \Sigma \rangle \\ &\rightleftharpoons \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle . \end{aligned}$$

The integral is equal to the limit of the sum of the terms of the series as infinity tends to n : $\text{Subscript}[\mathcal{L}, \text{Subscript}[f, \uparrow r, \alpha, s, \delta, \eta]] = \Omega - \sum \text{Subscript}[\bar{\psi}, \text{Subscript}[g, \neg a, b, c, d, e \dots \neg]] \, d\theta^n = \Omega\theta + C$

$$\begin{aligned} \cup \langle \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \rangle &= = o \langle \theta, \lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle \ni \Sigma \langle \xi, \pi, \rho, \sigma \rangle = = \Omega \langle \upsilon, \phi, \chi, \psi \rangle \\ &\ni K \langle \omega, \Theta, \Lambda, M \rangle \\ &\ni \Pi \langle \Xi, \Pi, P, \Sigma \rangle \\ &\ni \Omega \langle \Upsilon, \Phi, X, \Psi \rangle \\ \text{as } n &\rightarrow \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned}$$